

Interdependent design and operation of solar photovoltaics and battery energy storage for economically viable decarbonisation of local energy systems

Dacheng Li^{a,*}, Songshan Guo^b, Jihong Wang^c, Yongliang Li^a, Chenggong Sun^a, Geng Qiao^d, Chaomurilige^d, Yulong Ding^a

^a Birmingham Centre for Energy Storage, School of Chemical Engineering, University of Birmingham, Edgbaston, Birmingham, B15 2TT, UK

^b Minety Battery Storage Limited, Reading, RG1 1LX, UK

^c School of Engineering, University of Warwick, Coventry, CV4 7AL, UK

^d Global Energy Interconnection Research Institute Europe GmbH, Berlin, 10623, Germany

HIGHLIGHTS

- Interdependent economic optimisation of solar PVs and BESS for energy decarbonisation.
- A new framework combining artificial networks and upgraded evolutionary algorithms.
- Exploration of broader profit margins under diverse trading mechanisms with the DSO.
- Payback cycle can exceed system lifetime due to intensive BESS use in DA trading.
- Optimal solar PV scale is limited by NM participation of BESS energy stored via DFH.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Interdependent optimisation
Design
Operation
Techno-economic modelling
Economic flow
Artificial network
Intelligent framework

ABSTRACT

Local energy systems are undergoing significant transformation by integrating more solar photovoltaics (PVs) and battery energy storage systems (BESS) to achieve net-zero targets in the energy sector. To ensure an affordable and sustainable decarbonisation process, optimising both system design and operation together is crucial for maximising system profitability and encouraging broader stakeholder participation in the energy transition. However, the complex interdependent influence on the system economic flows, along with the nonlinear characteristics of the system, make the economic optimisation extremely challenging. To address this, we developed a new framework based on advanced artificial intelligence to exploit a wider arbitrage margin under various trading mechanisms, including net metering, day-ahead, and dynamic frequency. We conducted optimisation study on a local energy system operating at University of Warwick using real data from

Abbreviations: BBO, biogeography-based optimisation; BESS, battery energy storage system; CHP, combined heat and power; DA, day-ahead; DF, dynamic frequency; DSO, distributed system operator; DOD, depth of discharge; GBP, great Britain pound; HSI, habitat suitability index; PV, photovoltaic; NM, net metering; SOC, state of charge; ToU, time-of-use.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: d.li.6@bham.ac.uk (D. Li).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyai.2025.100505>

Available online 19 March 2025

2666-5468/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

demonstrated BESS and solar PVs, and the effectiveness of the proposed intelligent approach was validated, and the necessity of interdependent optimisation was highlighted. Results showed that, compared to the original campus system (20 MW-level), a carbon reduction rate of up to 61.4 % was achieved through net metering trading, while a maximum annual profit increase of 251 % was realised with dynamic frequency trading. The proposed intelligent framework can be applied to any energy systems with integrated solar PVs and BESS, where the adopted trading mechanism are associated with the system design and operation. The findings offer a practical tool for academics, investors, and policy makers to collaborate in the deployment of renewable energy and energy storage to accelerate the decarbonisation of energy supply.

Nomenclature		η	efficiency
a	parameter of power ratio model for DF service	<i>Subscripts</i>	
b	parameter of power ratio model for DF service	battery	battery
C	unit cost, $\text{GBP}\cdot\text{kWh}^{-1}$	DFH	high-frequency response
cl	cycle life, day	DFL	low-frequency response
f	daily cost, GBP	ec	engineering construction
fr	frequency, Hz	elec	electricity
i	i th time segment	energy	energy
IC	investment cost, GBP	fix	fixed
lt	lifetime	grid	grid
n	total number of time segment	inverter	inverter
N	number of devices	J	J th generation
OC	operation cost, GBP	K	K element
P	power, kW	local	local
Q	capacity, kWh	loss	loss
R	ratio	lower	lower limit
t	time, h	penalty	penalty
X	element in solution	PV	photovoltaic
<i>Greek symbols</i>		rated	rated
α	reference DOD	residual	residual
β	reference discharging rate	solar	solar
γ	actual discharging rate	supply	supply
Δt	time interval, h	system	system
ε	amplitude of disturbance	trade	trade
		upper	upper limit

1. Introduction

To achieve the decarbonisation targets of energy supply and mitigate climate change, energy systems are experiencing substantial transitions towards more distributed and local generation, driven by the rapidly increased renewable energy integration [1]. The role of local generation systems is evolving from energy consumers to energy prosumers. Among various renewable energy sources, solar photovoltaics (PVs) have solidified its leading role in the global energy transition to the clean and sustainable energy source and dominated the newly added global power generation capacity. According to SolarPower Europe [2], global capacity of the solar PVs surpassed 1.6 TW in 2023, installing over three times more capacity than all other renewable technologies combined, and is projected to reach 5.1 TW by 2028. This surge in the solar PV installation is mainly attributed to severe reduction in manufacturing costs and growing consensus around solar PVs as a reliable and economically feasible solution to rising energy prices. Additionally, the compact modular design and minimal geographic limitations is beneficial to the increasing introduction of the solar PVs into the local energy systems [3,4].

Despite contribution to the sustainable energy supply, there is often a mismatch between the generation and demand for electricity in local energy system integrated with solar PVs due to the intermittent and stochastic nature of solar irradiation [5]. When the production of the electricity falls short of local consumption, the energy gap is filled by the

power purchased from the grid. Conversely, when excess electricity is generated, the surplus electrical power is fed into the grid without gaining revenue or transacted with the Distributed System Operator (DSO) to obtain economic profits if an export license is issued. Introducing the electrical energy storage can facilitate the mitigation of the temporal energy imbalances, improve the energy self-sufficiency, and increase economic gains by autonomously determining the timing of energy transactions for a better rate [6,7]. While a variety of approaches have been conducted to explore reliable electrical energy storage technologies [8], the most notable technology is battery energy storage which has been successfully commercialised characterising with the advantages of high energy density, high coulombic efficiency, and fast response [9]. Additionally, mature trading markets have been established for the battery energy storage system (BESS) to offer ancillary services under various mechanisms, further enhancing economic benefits. Therefore, given the technique barriers and geographic limitations, the combination of solar PVs and BESS is adopted as a promising solution for the decarbonisation of local energy systems, particularly in residential sectors [10], attracting numerous investigations to analyse techno-economic performance of the system. Mendes et al., [11] demonstrated that integrating solar PVs and BESS in small-scale residential energy systems improves self-consumption and self-sufficiency. Pena-Bello et al., [12] developed an open-source framework for a PV-coupled battery system and identified the best-suited battery storage technologies under various combination of system operations to improve economic indicators. As a complementary study, Irshad et al.

[13] focused on selecting efficient PV technologies for battery hybrid systems based on geographical location to reduce net present costs. To explore the economics of solar-plus-storage projects for commercial-scale, McLaren et al. [14] investigated the influence of various factors on the economic viability of energy systems. A national scale analysis was conducted and the outcome identified that the primary drivers of system economics were technology cost and utility rates.

To successfully achieve net-zero emission in the coming decades, it is essential to enhance the performance of local energy systems through the optimal design and operation of the solar PVs and BESS. The attractive benefits achieved could bring together academics, investors, and policy makers to cooperate for contributing to the energy system transition. In this regard, extensive optimisation approaches have been carried out and can be classified into two categories. The first category focuses on optimising either the design or operation of the renewables and energy storage. Pan et al. [15] determined the optimal capacity of the solar PV (kW) and battery energy storage (kWh) for a grid-connected household using a rule-based energy management strategy according to the flat and time-of-use (ToU) tariffs. Two configurations of PV only and PV-BESS were adopted in the optimisation to achieve a less cost of the system. Huang et al. [16] proposed a hierarchical design optimisation method for distributed batteries in solar-power shared building communities. The research aimed to reduce the equipped battery capacity and minimise the energy loss in the sharing process. Duan et al. [17] worked on a multi-objective framework for a hybrid microgrid including PV, wind turbine, and battery energy storage. Optimisation of the capacity of the system components was implemented to minimise the annual energy losses, voltage oscillations, and the cost of purchasing power. Tian et al. [18] considered more types of system components and targeted at a complementary system of hydra-wind-PV-battery and proposed an optimal capacity planning framework. Considering the characteristics of multi-energy integration into power grid, the capacities of components were optimised to ensure effective utilisation of resources and best system performance. From the operational perspective, Jayawardana et al. [19] developed a framework to optimally control battery charge and discharge within a microgrid containing a solar PV system. The benefits for bringing economic gains compared to the fixed control method was validated and the importance of the consideration of the battery operating cost was highlighted. In [20], an optimisation model was developed to control the battery operation for a PV generation system to maximise the revenue stream of feed-in tariff incentive. Different electricity rates and storage unit costs were considered in the optimisation and the impact of battery storage capacity on the objective function was evaluated. It is worthy to note that, the previous approaches mentioned above did not incorporate the operation-dependent battery degradation and its associated costs in the optimisation process, which play a pivotal role for determining the energy and economic performance [21,22].

The second category involves optimising both the design and operation of renewables and energy storage. Samantaray and Kayal [23] proposed an optimal strategy to determine the size and charging/discharging scheduling of the battery storage in PV integrated distribution systems. Multi-optimisation for improving the technical performance and reliability of distributed energy system was implemented by minimising load demand deviations and active power loss. Baniasadi et al. [24] developed an optimal framework for sizing design and real-time operation of BESS and thermal storage system in a residential building equipped with a PV system. A model predictive controller was developed to minimise daily electricity and life cycle costs of a smart building. Arthur et al. [25] presented an optimisation model for determining the selection and operation of decentralised PV and battery energy systems for commercial buildings. Two management plans of ToU bill management and frequency response were considered for the battery in the forming of operation strategy to maximise revenue potential. Despite recognising the need to consider system design in conjunction with the operation, many prior studies relied on the energy shortage to determine

the optimal operation of BESS and are subject to many restrictions from pre-defined strategies. Such inadequate optimisation solution can result in a further broad optimisation space being unexplored.

To accelerate the decarbonisation of energy supply, it is necessary to mobilise the stakeholders by leveraging economic incentives to drive participation in local energy system transitions. However, in addition to the research gaps demonstrated above, it is extremely challenging to meet the desired goal of system affordability owing to the complex interdependencies between system design and operation, which affect economic flows. On the one hand, the design scheme, such as total capacity, rated power of the BESS and solar PVs, determines capital investment and operation cost associated with the calendar lifetimes. On the other hand, the operation strategy, such as time and power of charging, discharging the battery, and output path of the solar power, decides the capital revenue from the energy self-sufficiency and the depreciation expenditure induced by the operation-dependant cycle life reduction. In this context, the optimal selection of the design parameters is influenced by the operation-dependant cost (aging), and conversely, the optimal formulation of the operating plan is affected by the design-dependant ability of renewable generation and power shifting to bring in economic benefits. These factors are coupled and interactively affect the economic viability of energy systems against the variation of the load demands and solar irradiations. Moreover, these coupled interactions in the economic flow are further strengthened when trading mechanisms associated with the design and operation parameters are introduced for seeking a high system profitability. To address these challenges, an intelligent framework based on advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) is urgently needed for decoupling the intricate interdependencies in economic flows and dealing with the nonlinearities of system inherent in optimisation. These nonlinearities are embedded in renewables and load demands, performance and degradation of storage, and electricity market pricing structures with their corresponding constraints. Notably, AI-driven approaches are becoming indispensable for building smart energy systems capable of achieving energy decarbonisation targets [3, 26].

In this paper, we propose a new intelligent approach to simultaneously optimise the design and operation of solar PVs and BESS, providing economically viable solutions for local energy system decarbonisation. To our best knowledge, this is one of the first studies to use AI to decouple complicated interactions associated with the economic flows in solar PV and BESS integrated energy systems while accounting for extreme nonlinearities in optimisation. The remaining paper is organised as follows. Coupled mathematical models are developed to bridge the decision variables of optimisation to the economic flows of the energy system. Then artificial networks are built to determine all the reasonable energy flow routes under the decision variables and different trading mechanisms. Afterwards, we established an intelligent optimisation framework by combining the developed networks with an upgraded evolutionary algorithm to improve the economic performance of the energy system. A Combined Heat and Power (CHP) system at the University of Warwick (UoW), a scaled-down model of a city, is adopted as the target system and the optimisation results and system performance under different scenarios are detailed discussed and compared to clarify the optimisation mechanisms and validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach. A conclusion of the paper is provided by emphasising the broader implications of this work for economically viable decarbonisation in the energy sector.

2. Techno-economic coupled modelling

2.1. Investment cost modelling

Based on empirical data from utility-scale application [27], the investment cost of the BESS depends on the installed capacity and configured power, which can be defined as follows.

$$IC_{\text{BESS}} = C_{\text{battery}} \times Q_{\text{battery}} \times N_{\text{battery}} \times R_{\text{ec}} + C_{\text{inverter}} \times R_{\text{inverter}} \times Q_{\text{battery}} \times N_{\text{battery}} \quad (1)$$

where C_{battery} , Q_{battery} , and N_{battery} refer to the unit price, capacity, and total number of the battery; R_{ec} refers to the cost increase ratio induced by the engineering construction; and C_{inverter} and R_{inverter} refer to the unit price and power ratio of the inverter, respectively.

On the other hand, the investment cost of solar system can be evaluated by the installed capacity of the PV panels [28,29], which can be modelled by:

$$IC_{\text{solar}} = C_{\text{PV}} \times P_{\text{PV}} \times N_{\text{PV}} \quad (2)$$

where C_{PV} , P_{PV} , and N_{PV} refer to the investment cost and capacity per unit, and number of the solar PV.

2.2. Operation cost modelling

The depreciation expense due to the cycle life reduction of the integrated solar PV modules and BESS constitutes the operation costs of the system. For the battery, cycle life reduction is attributed to capacity fade, which is mainly influenced by working temperature, Depth of Discharge (DOD), and discharging capacity rate (C-rate) [30]. Assuming an efficient cooling system is adopted for regulating the working temperature of the batteries to the normal working status (20 °C), the DOD and C-rate are considered in the cycle life model. Referring to [31], the capacity fade of the battery is proportional to the increases in the DOD and discharging C-rate. Using reference values α for DOD and β for discharging C-rate, the residual cycle life of the battery after time t under γ discharging C-rate can be represented by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} cl_{\text{residual}}(t+1)|_{\alpha,\beta} &= cl_{\text{residual}}(t)|_{\alpha,\beta} - cl_{\text{loss}}(t)|_{\alpha,\beta} \\ &= cl_{\text{residual}}(t)|_{\alpha,\beta} - \frac{cl_{\text{rated}}|_{\alpha,\beta}}{cl_{\text{rated}}|_{\alpha,\gamma(t)}} \frac{\text{SOC}(t) - \text{SOC}(t+1)}{\alpha} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where cl_{residual} , cl_{loss} , and cl_{rated} refer to the residual, loss, and rated cycle life of the battery, respectively. Taking the calendar lifetime of the battery into account, the daily operation cost of the batteries induced by the cycle life reduction can be calculated as:

$$OC_{\text{battery}} = C_{\text{battery}} \times Q_{\text{battery}} \times N_{\text{battery}} \times R_{\text{ec}} \times \max \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n cl_{\text{loss}}(i)|_{\alpha,\beta}}{cl_{\text{rated}}|_{\alpha,\beta}}, \frac{1}{lt_{\text{battery}}} \right) \quad (4)$$

where n refers to the total number of the time segments in an operation cycle, and lt_{battery} refers to the calendar lifetime of the battery. On the other hand, the daily operation cost of the inverter can be calculated by

$$OC_{\text{inverter}} = \frac{C_{\text{inverter}} \times R_{\text{inverter}} \times Q_{\text{battery}} \times N_{\text{battery}}}{lt_{\text{inverter}}} \quad (5)$$

where lt_{inverter} refers to the calendar lifetime of the inverter.

The battery can operate in charging, discharging, or standby modes. The SOC of the battery at the time $t+1$ during charging and discharging processes can be represented by the following equation [32].

$$\begin{cases} \text{Charging : } \text{SOC}(t+1) = \text{SOC}(t) + \frac{P_{\text{charge}}(t)\eta\Delta t}{Q_{\text{battery}}} \\ \text{Discharging : } \text{SOC}(t+1) = \text{SOC}(t) - \frac{P_{\text{discharge}}(t)\Delta t}{\eta Q_{\text{battery}}} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where P_{charge} and $P_{\text{discharge}}$ refer to the charging and discharging power of the battery; η refers to the round-trip efficiency of the battery; and Δt refers to the time interval. To guarantee the safety and resilience of the

battery system, the SOC should be regulated in a region as [32]

$$\text{SOC}_{\text{lower}} \leq \text{SOC}(t) \leq \text{SOC}_{\text{upper}} \quad (7)$$

where $\text{SOC}_{\text{lower}}$ and $\text{SOC}_{\text{upper}}$ refer to the lower and upper limits of the SOC. Additionally, for effective battery management and preparation for the next cycle of operation to achieve greater economic benefits, the accordance of the SOC at the start and end of each operation cycle needs to be guaranteed in the real operation, which is

$$\text{SOC}(t_{\text{start}}) = \text{SOC}(t_{\text{end}}) \quad (8)$$

For the solar PV modules, the cycle life reduction under extreme environmental conditions was not considered in this study [33,34], and the daily operation cost is represented as

$$OC_{\text{solar}} = \frac{IC_{\text{solar}}}{lt_{\text{PV}}} \quad (9)$$

where lt_{PV} refers to the calendar lifetime of the PV module.

2.3. Electricity price modelling

Time of Use (ToU) pricing is a rate structure reflecting the cost associated with electricity production throughout the day [35]. Generally, ToU tariffs involve high-peak, flat-peak, and low-peak periods, and this price differentiation is one of the main drivers of energy arbitrage by using BESS. Based on the schedule of charge provided by the WPD PLC. UK, the electricity purchasing price from the grid can be demonstrated using the following equation [36].

$$C_{\text{elec}} = C_{\text{ToU}} + C_{\text{fix}} \quad (10)$$

where C_{ToU} and C_{fix} refer to the ToU tariffs and fixed charge, respectively.

2.4. Trading mechanism modelling

Participation in trading with the DSO can bring economic benefits to the owner of the local energy system. Net metering (NM), day-ahead (DA), and dynamic frequency (DF) services are common trading services available in the current energy market [37]. For net metering, surplus energy from the local energy system can be sold to the grid at the electricity purchasing price C_{ele} instead of being exported without profits. In day-ahead trading, stored electricity in the BESS can be managed and sold at the time-varied price C_{DA} on the day prior to delivery day. The trading price is typically higher than C_{ele} , which can contribute to providing sufficient profit margin for introducing battery energy storage. In this study, dynamic containment was chosen as a representative dynamic frequency service. For DF services, the operating power of the BESS can be adjusted to meet the requirement of frequency response, including low-frequency response (DFL) and high-frequency response (DFH). Based on a valid bid, the service fee obtained from the frequency management can be expressed as follows:

$$C_{\text{DF}} = \begin{cases} C_{\text{DFH}} + C_{\text{DFL}}, & (\text{DFH and DFL are valid}); \\ C_{\text{DFH}}, & (\text{DFH is valid}); \\ C_{\text{DFL}}, & (\text{DFL is valid}); \\ 0, & (\text{DFH and DFL are not valid}). \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where C_{DFL} and C_{DFH} refer to the service fee of the DFL and DFH, respectively. The ratio of battery power for the DF service can be calculated using the following equations [38].

$$\begin{cases} R_{\text{DFL}} = -a_1 \times fr + b_1 \\ R_{\text{DFH}} = a_2 \times fr - b_2 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where R_{DFL} and R_{DFH} refer to the ratio of discharging power and charging power for the DF service, a and b refer to the parameters obtained according to the specification provided, and fr refers to the grid

frequency.

3. Interdependent optimisation method

3.1. Optimisation model

The optimisation aim of the research is to achieve the minimum cost in electricity supply (or maximum profits) of local energy system by integrating the BESS and solar PVs. The objective function can be formulated as follows:

$$\min f = \min \sum (f_{\text{system}} + f_{\text{energy}} - f_{\text{trade}} + f_{\text{penalty}}) \quad (13)$$

In Eq. (13), the daily cost of system operation, f_{system} , consists of the depreciation expense of BESS and PVs, which can be demonstrated as

$$f_{\text{system}} = (OC_{\text{battery}} + OC_{\text{inverter}} + OC_{\text{solar}}) \quad (14)$$

The daily energy expenditure, f_{energy} , includes the electricity bill for filling the load shortage and the energy purchasing cost for charging the batteries, which can be shown as

$$f_{\text{energy}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \{ C_{\text{elec}}(i) \times \Delta t \times [P_{\text{grid}}(i) + \max(0, P_{\text{load}}(i) - P_{\text{local}}(i) - P_{\text{PV}}(i) \times N_{\text{PV}} - P_{\text{supply}}(i) \times N_{\text{battery}})] \} \quad (15)$$

where P_{grid} refers to the electricity purchased from grid for charging the battery; P_{load} and P_{local} refer to electricity load of the users and non-renewable power generation of the local energy system, respectively; and P_{supply} refers to power supplied from the BESS to compensate the load demand.

The three representative service modes discussed in the Section 2.4 were referred to model the daily profit gains from the trading with the DSO. The net metering can combine with either DA trading or DF service, and the economic benefits yield from the trading transactions can be demonstrated as,

$$f_{\text{trade}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[P_{\text{NM}}(i) \times C_{\text{elec}}(i) \times \Delta t + \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (P_{\text{DA}}(i) \times N_{\text{battery}} \times C_{\text{DA}}(i) \times \Delta t) \parallel \\ (Q_{\text{battery}} \times N_{\text{battery}} \times R_{\text{inverter}} \times C_{\text{DF}}(i) \times \Delta t) \end{array} \right\} \right] \quad (16)$$

where P_{NM} refers to the surplus power from the energy system for the net metering, and P_{DA} refers to the power discharged from the BESS for participating in the day-ahead trading.

A penalty, f_{penalty} , is imposed on system operations when the input or output power exceeds the substation capacity limit, thereby avoiding threats to the safety and resilience of substation and costly substation upgrades.

Referring to the objective function, the decision variables ought to be optimised can be classified into design and operation variables. The number of the installed batteries (N_{battery}) and solar PVs (N_{PV}), and the maximum power ratio of the inverter (R_{inverter}) relative to the rated capacity of the battery (1C) need to be determined in the early deployment stage and were categorised as the design variables. On the other hand, the initial SOC and operating power of the batteries in each time segment (P_{charge} and $P_{\text{discharge}}$) were set as the operation variables. Additionally, flags which indicate the operation modes of the battery and the participation in trading transaction were also adopted as operation variables to facilitate the development of the optimal searching process. Pre-judgment of the energy flow direction for the BESS using the flags can simplify the logic of artificial network for the optimisation and is beneficial to enhance the optimising capabilities by increasing the diversity of the solution components and narrowing the searching range for battery operating power.

3.2. Artificial network development

The logic process of the artificial network is shown in Fig. 1, which starts from the evaluation for the necessity of pre-action to align the battery SOC at the initial and final points of each operation cycle. The required number of time segments for pre-action of the BESS were calculated by the following equation based on the upper and lower limits of the SOC and the selected minimum power ratio of the inverter,

$$n_{\text{pre-charge}} = \text{ceiling} \left(\frac{\text{SOC}_{\text{upper}} - \text{SOC}_{\text{lower}}}{R_{\text{inverter}}^{\text{lower}} \times \Delta t \times \eta} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$n_{\text{pre-discharge}} = \text{ceiling} \left(\frac{\text{SOC}_{\text{upper}} - \text{SOC}_{\text{lower}}}{R_{\text{inverter}}^{\text{lower}} \times \Delta t / \eta} \right) \quad (18)$$

where $n_{\text{pre-charge}}$ and $n_{\text{pre-discharge}}$ refer to number of time segments required for pre-charging and pre-discharging the BESS, respectively.

If the segment number i is greater or equal to $n - n_{\text{pre-charge}}$ or $n - n_{\text{pre-discharge}}$, the evaluation of the battery SOC is conducted to check whether current SOC is located in two extreme conditions where either charging or discharging behaviour should be compulsively implemented. If so, following the dashed line, the corresponding operating power of the battery is defined based on the minimum chargeable or dischargeable SOC under the selected inverter ratio. Alternatively, if the SOC of the battery is not in the extreme conditions in the current segment or the segment number is less than $n - n_{\text{pre-charge}}$ or $n - n_{\text{pre-discharge}}$ in the first place, the operation modes of the BESS will be determined randomly by the flags in optimal searching process. In this case, the upper and lower limits of SOC will be also adopted to restrict the charging or discharging power of the battery to mitigate the safety concerns during the operation.

Proceeding further, when the batteries run in charging mode (Battery flag is 1), Sub process I is triggered, where the cycle life reduction of the batteries from the discharging behaviour is ignored, and no battery power is released for trading service. If the trading price for the DA service, E_{DA} , is identified as positive, the DFH service is not applicable for BESS, and corresponding economic gains C_{DF} are zero. The logic flow then moves to internal network II, which compare the local energy production with the sum of load demand and the energy consumption for battery charging to determine the amount of the energy purchased from the grid or the surplus energy that could participate in the net metering trading transaction. When the trading price of DA is not available, the activation of the DFH service is determined based on the current grid frequency, maximum chargeable power, and the corresponding flag for DFH trading (DFH flag). If BESS participates in the DFH service, the power for battery charging from the grid would not be accounted in the expense calculations, and the surplus energy available for net metering is determined in internal network I.

If the BESS is assigned to a discharging mode (Battery flag is 2), following the Sub process II, no grid power is import for charging the batteries and the flag for DFH service is set to 0. The utilisation of the energy from the battery discharging is determined by a series of logic judgement. When the E_{DA} is identified as positive, the flag of discharge for trading (TD flag) is adopted to determine the participation in DA trading. If the TD flag is identified as 1, the discharging power from the battery is traded to the grid under DA trading price and the surplus power available from the local system for net metering is quantified in internal network I. While, if the TD flag is deactivated, the discharged energy from the BESS can be utilised to compensate the local demand, resulting in an increase in the amount of surplus energy for net metering trading in internal network III. The participation in the DFL service will be considered when E_{DA} is identified as invalid. The comparisons of current grid frequency to the f_{lower} and the required DFL power to the maximum dischargeable battery power are conducted, and the activation of the TD flag is evaluated. If all the conditions are met, the

Fig. 1. Artificial network for economic optimisation (decision variables are marked as red) (A) Main artificial network, (B) Internal artificial network.

discharge power of the battery will be set equal to the P_{DFL} , and the energy for net metering trading will be determined in internal network I. If the conditions for implementing DFL service is judged as not applicable, the power of the BESS is released to the local energy system and the potential energy for net metering export will be evaluated in internal network III. It is worth noting that the TD flag is adopted as an operation variable for determining either the participation in the DA service or DFL service, which can facilitate the reduction of variables for economic optimisation.

If the battery flag is deactivated ($= 0$), the BESS will stay at standby mode and the surplus energy that can be traded with grid is evaluated in internal network I. The logic flow goes into Sub process III: batteries cease working and the flags for DF trading turn to 0. No grid power is import for charging the batteries and no depreciation expense occur by the discharging behaviour of the battery. If the E_{DA} is identified as positive, the profit gain from the DF service is not available; while, if not, economic benefits are achievable when the current grid frequency lies

between f_{lower} and f_{upper} .

The economic optimisation without any trading mechanisms could also be conducted using the developed artificial network through setting all trading service prices to zero.

3.3. Intelligent optimisation framework

To achieve the best combination of the decision variables to optimise the objective function, the integration of the artificial network with the improved evolutionary algorithm was implemented. In this work, the Biogeography-Based Optimisation (BBO) approach is adopted as the basic algorithm owing to its rapid self-convergence and predominant robustness [39], to build an intelligent framework. Detailed operating mechanism of the framework is investigated and illustrated as follows in sequence:

I. Definition process: the data related to the coupled models are collected and input into the framework; matrixes containing zero

vectors of different dimensions are designed for the decision variables and condition parameters of the system operation; optimal searching ranges for the decision variables are defined.

II. Initialisation process: The parameters related to the evolutionary algorithm are initialised, including the total population size (number of the solution vector), generation count limit, number of the elements in each population (number of the decision variables), mutation probability, elitism parameter, maximum migration rate, and max species count. Then, a random set (contains quantity of population size) of habitats that represents the design scheme and control strategy of the energy system is generated.

III. Iterative process: The Habitat Suitability Index (HSI) (objective value) for each habitat from the control segment (time segment) $i = 1$ to dimension n is calculated using artificial network demonstrated in Fig. 1; then the HSIs are mapped to the species count.

IV. Termination evaluation: The operation of the framework ends when the generation count limit is reached; otherwise, continues to go to [V. Optimisation process].

V. Optimisation process: Probabilistic migration and mutation of non-elite habitat is implemented; essentially, a random disturbance mimicking artificial domestication theory [40] is introduced to best solutions (not including the flag) from the previous generation to produce new individuals of habitat for next iterative process. The process can be presented as

$$X_K(J+1) = X_K(J) + \text{round}(\varepsilon \times \text{unifrnd}(-1, 1))$$

where $X_K(J)$ refers to the element K in the selected best solution at J th generation, and ε refers to amplitude of the disturbance determined by the characteristics of the element.

VI. Legalisation process: The feasibility of the new generated solutions is examined, and the values of the decision variables are restricted using the defined searching ranges. Then the process switches to [III. Iterative process].

4. Optimisation results and discussions

A CHP system at the University of Warwick was adopted as the target local energy system (20 MW-level). Operating in a “thermal lead” mode, the electricity generation of the CHPs is determined by the thermal load on campus. The supply gap of the electricity is filled by imports from the grid, while surplus electricity produced by the CHPs is exported to the grid without any profit gain because the University currently does not hold an export licence. To reduce electricity purchasing cost and achieve decarbonisation of the energy supply, the University has been in the process of deploying a 6 MW-level solar PV system. The power output of the PVs mainly depends on the solar irradiation and ambient temperature. Based on the historic operation data of 248 kW-level solar PVs that were already arranged in the campus, the electrical energy generation intensity per installed solar PV unit throughout a full year was demonstrated in Fig. 2. The corresponding weather conditions can be accessed by visiting the “Time and Date” website [41]. It can be learned that more solar energy is available during the spring and summer seasons. Since weather conditions and solar irradiation are relatively stable each year at the same location, energy generation intensity was directly used to calculate the energy output of upscaled solar PV systems at the same site. Assuming the planned scale of the solar system (6 MW) is installed on campus, taking the year of 2022 as an example, the net electricity discrepancy in energy supply (= CHP generation + solar PVs generation – load demand) can be obtained, as shown in Fig. 3. Large energy shortage can be observed throughout the year, which result in high electricity bills for purchasing energy from the grid. Integrating a BESS into the campus energy system could contribute to smoothing the energy discrepancy, providing a solution for reducing the expenditure in energy supply based on the ToU pricing structure and through participation in the trading transaction if an export license is issued. Additionally,

Fig. 2. Annual distribution of electrical energy generation intensity per installed solar PV unit.

Fig. 3. Net electricity discrepancy in 2022 with 6 MW-level solar PVs.

surplus energy of the local generation, which can be further augmented by introducing more solar PVs, could either be stored in the BESS or take part in the energy trading. It is worthy to note that, the introduction of the BESS could contribute to preventing the potential expansion of campus substation capacity in response to rising energy consumption and generation. If the achieved economic income could offset the energy bill for load demand and compensate operating cost of the system, and even avoid expensive upgrade of power network infrastructure, it would greatly encourage the investors to participate in the development of Solar PVs and BESS within the energy supply.

To evaluate the annual economic performance of the campus energy system with the introduction of optimal renewable energy and battery energy storage, as shown in Fig. 4, the electrical energy distribution for a typical day, characterised the average CHP electricity generation (determined by the thermal load) and the average power generation of solar PVs for each season, was selected and arranged in sequence to simplify the modelling of energy discrepancy over the entire year. Each day was equally divided into 48-time segments by a half hour, resulting in a total of 192 time segments for optimisation of the system behaviour for a full year.

As shown in Fig. 5, a demonstration of BESS, which was composed of a battery stack (lithium-ion cell), bidirectional inverters, transformers,

Fig. 4. Electrical energy distribution of the Campus in 2022 with 6 MW-level solar PVs.

Fig. 5. Diagram of the demonstration BESS.

and a data acquisition platform, was developed in the current study. We tested the BESS to obtain the experiment data for developing operation model for optimisation (see Fig. S1 in the **supplementary material**). Considering the stable charging/discharging efficiency across a wide range of operating power and SOC (see Fig. S1C) and a low SOC reduction rate during the standby process (see Fig. S1D), a constant round-trip efficiency of $\eta = 90\%$ was adopted for the BESS and the SOC loss during the standby process was neglected in the optimisation. Generally, a battery is considered out of service when residual capacity drops to 80% of rated value [42]. Referring to Fig. S1A, operating at a lower C-rate for a same DOD led to less reduction in the cycle life: the rated cycle life of the battery increased from 6650 to 7075 and 7775 when the discharging C-rate varied from 1C to 0.5C and 0.1C at 90% DOD. Taking the 90% DOD (α) and 1 C-rate (β) as a reference condition, a power law expression was applied to represent the rated cycle life at a γ C-rate with 90% DOD for the battery, as shown in Eq. (19):

$$c_{\text{rated}}|_{90\%,\gamma} = (1/\gamma)^{0.07} c_{\text{rated}}|_{90\%,1\text{C}} \quad (19)$$

where 90%, γ and 90%,1C refer to the conditions where 90% DOD occurs at a discharging C-rate of γ and 1C, respectively.

As shown in Table 1, the charge schedule provided by the WPD was adopted to present the electricity purchasing price from the grid [36].

The constants for the techno-economic coupled models are provided in Table S1, based on the engineering projects from authors' institution and Refs. [28,29], while the parameters associated with the optimisation process are given in Table S2 in the **supplementary material**. By

Table 1
Schedule of electricity charge ($\times 10^{-2}$ GBP.kWh $^{-1}$).

C_{ToU}	C_{ToU}	C_{ToU}	C_{fix}
High-peak (16:00 to 19:00)	Flat-peak (07:30 to 16:00 to 19:00 to 21:00)	Low-peak (00:00 to 7:30 21:00 to 24:00)	(00:00 to 24:00)
6.077	1.079	0.127	10.41

inputting these models and parameters and implementing the intelligent framework demonstrated in Section 3, optimisation solutions including the optimal combination of decision variables for various scenarios were investigated, and the performance of the local energy system was analysed and compared. The optimal results and overall system performance under different scenarios is illustrated and compared in Table 2 and Fig. 6.

4.1. System performance without energy trading (Scenario II)

According to the current University policy, energy trading is not permitted. In this context, the optimisation results recommended an integration of a 19.89 MW-level solar PVs without battery installation for the campus energy system to achieve maximum economic benefits. The capacity of the PV system was determined according to the optimal balance between investment expenditure and profit gains from filling the energy demand. Compared to the current scheme of 6 MW-level PV installation, the enlargement of solar scale could contribute to narrowing annual energy shortage from 38.63 GWh to 31.64 GWh and reduce the corresponding electricity purchasing cost from 4.59 million (m) GBP to 3.75 m GBP. Although an additional annual depreciation expense of 0.69 m GBP was needed for the solar system upgrade, as shown in Fig. 6A, the annual cost of campus energy system decreased from 4.89 m GBP (Scenario I) to 4.75 m GBP.

Due to the absence of a trading mechanism, a total of 3.93 GWh and 2.25 MWh campus-generated energy were exported to the grid in the spring and winter seasons, respectively, without any profit gain returned. The high investment cost of the BESS and the limited availability of surplus energy from the campus hindered the introduction of batteries to the campus energy system. Specifically, considering the charging and discharging efficiency of the BESS ($\eta = 0.9$), the profit margins from offsetting high-peak loads with surplus energy or low-peak electricity were 13.35 and 4.82 p.kWh $^{-1}$, respectively. Meanwhile, the minimum daily cost of the BESS obtained based on the calendar lifetime (10 years for batteries and 20 years for inverters) was over 12.3 p.kWh $^{-1}$. This price composition indicates that, to obtain economic benefits by conducting peak-shaving using the BESS, a sufficient surplus of energy ought to be provided across seasons, and sole storing low-peak electricity to later fill high-peak energy gap is not economically feasible. In the current case, the integration of the BESS could yield profits in the spring and winter seasons through high-peak shaving but would fall short in other seasons owing to a lack of surplus energy. Overall, the total economic gains from BESS operations would not be sufficient to cover its depreciation cost, leading to a deficit for the campus energy system.

4.2. System performance with introduction of net metering trading (Scenario III)

When the net metering trading was introduced, the situation of energy export without economic compensation encountered in the above case can be avoided. The optimisation results indicated that the BESS was still not an economically viable option for reducing high-peak energy shortage or participating in energy trading because its high cost exceeded the available interest margin. Conversely, integrating more solar PVs to increase surplus energy exports from the campus at net metering prices could help yield economic benefits. This is because, for

Table 2
Optimal results and system performance under different scenarios.

Case Results	Scenario I (Original system integrated with a 6 MW solar PVs)	Scenario II (Optimisation without trading mechanism)	Scenario III (Optimisation with net metering trading)	Scenario IV (Optimisation with net metering trading and day-ahead trading)	Scenario V (Optimisation with net metering trading and dynamic frequency trading)
Solar PV capacity (MW)	6	19.89	35.93	35.93	23.52
Battery capacity (MWh)	–	–	–	22.54	175
Maximum power ratio of the inverter (C-rate)	–	–	–	0.69	1
Load met by the grid, solar PVs, and BESS (%)	89.1, 10.9, -	73, 27, -	59.8, 40.2, -	59.8, 40.2, 0	69.5, 30.5, 0
Battery charged by the grid and solar PVs (%)	–	–	–	94, 6	100, 0
Annual Net Economic Flow = $-f$ (Eq. (13)) (Million GBP)	-4.89	-4.75	-3.6	0.73	7.37
Carbon emission (Ton per year)	8051	5755	3105	4002	5388
System lifetime (Year)	20	20	20	3.6	10
Payback cycle (Year)	–	16.7	10.8	4.1	4.8

each kW of solar PV installed, an annual revenue of 93.08 GBP could be received via filling the energy shortage or participating in net metering trading. After deducting depreciation cost, a net economic gain of 43.08 GBP per year would be available which indicated that the more installation of the PVs, the more economic income could be obtained. However, according to the optimisation results, the optimal capacity of the solar PVs only increased to 35.93 MW, remaining below the set upper limit (= 100 MW). This constraint occurred because of the consideration of the export limit of the substation capacity: in the 24th time segment of spring season, the electricity export from the campus energy system reached the maximum permissible value of 17.99 MW.

Under the provided energy configuration, the annual energy bill of filling energy shortage fell to 3.07 m GBP, and in the meantime, the campus could export 9.86 GWh, 112.24 MWh, and 50.02 MWh of electricity to the grid during the spring, autumn, and winter seasons, respectively, leading to a total income of 1.26 m GBP from net metering trading. Although the annual investment cost of PV system surged by 1.5 m GBP, referring to Fig. 6A, the total operating cost of the campus energy system decreased to 3.6 m GBP.

4.3. System performance with introduction of day-ahead trading (Scenario IV)

With the day-ahead trading mechanism, stored energy in the BESS can be exported to the DSO at the trading price shown in Fig. 7 [43], typically higher than the ToU rates for corresponding time segments. According to the optimisation results, a combined configuration of a 22.54 MWh BESS and a 0.69 C-rate of inverter, and a 35.93 MW solar PV system was proposed to achieve the best economic performance. The optimal operation strategy of the battery was shown in Fig. 8A and B, and the economic flow of campus energy system was depicted in Fig. 8C.

In the spring season, the optimal initial SOC of the batteries for each day was set to 0.29, and the operation cycle life of the battery reached 3.26. As depicted in Fig. 8A, the batteries were charged by partial surplus energy generated from the campus and electricity purchased from the grid, resulting in an expenditure of 6179 GBP per day. It is worth noting that, all released power from the batteries was then used to participate in the day-ahead trading in the high-price segments; while no contribution was made to reduce the discrepancy of energy demand, leading to an energy bill of 5507 GBP. Day-ahead trading behaviour of the BESS could bring a total income of 18,184 GBP, and an additional 10,012 GBP was earned from net metering of the surplus energy

produced from the campus energy system. After accounting for depreciation costs of the BESS and solar systems, which was 5610 GBP and 4922 GBP, respectively, the net profit of campus energy system was 5979 GBP per day during the spring season.

In the summer, the optimal initial SOC of batteries reached 0.77. As shown in Fig. 8A, the batteries were mainly charged by the grid power at low-peak and flat-peak rates, incurring a daily electricity cost of 4078 GBP. In addition, an energy bill of 11,239 GBP was generated to cover the campus energy shortage. It is worthy to mention that the operation cycle life of the batteries was optimised to 1.64, which was aligned with the value calculated by the calendar lifetime. This implied the situation that the introduction of the BESS in summer failed to bring profit gain, and the battery was making full use of its calendar cycle to reduce the economic loss through day-ahead trading. This claim can be proved by the following calculations: the depreciation expense of the BESS was 2885 GBP per day, and including the charging cost, a total expense of 6963 GBP was used in the BESS operation. The stored energy in the BESS was released to participate in the day-ahead trading, and 5943 GBP of income was obtained. Eventually, a net deficit of 1020 GBP was incurred with the BESS integration which was lower than the BESS depreciation cost. The occurrence of this situation stemmed from insufficient profit margins provided by the DSO between the day-ahead trading prices and ToU prices. The maximum margin of 9.87 p-kWh^{-1} was available in the 87th and 88th segments, which was below the minimum daily cost of the BESS per unit. Additionally, lack of surplus energy from the campus was another obstacle that hindered the profitability of using the BESS. In detail, the surplus energy, which was only available from the 71st to 73rd segments, was not adequate for the equipped batteries to run a whole cycle life to generate income. A trivial economic gain of 346 GBP was obtained via the net metering trading and the total daily deficit in the summer reached 16,835 GBP.

It can be learned from the Fig. 7; a relatively high day-ahead trading price was available in autumn. Given findings from the previous two cases, more active operation of the BESS was expected to capitalise on day-ahead trading opportunities. Referring to the optimisation results shown in Fig. 8B, the initial SOC of the battery was optimised to 0.15, and despite the scarcity of the surplus energy (available only in segment 116, 117, and 119), the operation cycle life of the batteries reached 7.03 and the corresponding depreciation cost elevated to 11,999 GBP. Nevertheless, numerous economic gains of 57,143 GBP were achieved through purchasing the electricity from the grid and selling it at a high day-ahead trading price. Similar to the summer case, an income of only

Fig. 6. Comparison of system performance under different scenarios (A) Net economic flow, (B) Carbon emission, (C) System lifetime, and (D) Payback cycle.

141 GBP was obtained via the net metering owing to the lack of the surplus energy availability. After covering electricity bill of 19,129 GBP for energy storage and 10,030 GBP for load compensation, a net profit of 11,205 GBP per day was achieved in autumn.

According to the Fig. 7, in the winter case, the provided day-ahead trading price was still high enough to motivate the operation of the batteries over the calendar cycles to achieve more economic gains. According to the optimisation results, the initial SOC of the battery was set to 0.11, and the operation cycle life was optimised to 6.49, leading to a depreciation expenditure of 11,072 GBP. Day-ahead trading yielded an income of 44,054 GBP, and an additional 312 GBP was earned from the net metering trading. An expense of 17,121 GBP occurred to purchase electricity from the grid for battery charging and an energy bill of 6887 GBP was generated for meeting campus load demand. Compared to autumn, the net profit of the campus energy system decreased to 4363 GBP per day which was mainly attributed to the relatively low day-ahead trading price.

Summing up the economic performance across the four seasons, as shown in Fig. 6A, an annual net profit of 0.73 m GBP could be achieved after deducting the operation costs of BESS and solar PVs. To fully clarify

the optimisation mechanism, further discussions are warranted on the following results. (i) The optimal capacity for solar PVs remained the same as in the net metering trading only scenario (III). The expected picture of utilising more renewable energy by integrating more BESS to guarantee the power export under the substation limit did not occur. One of the main reasons for this outcome could be attributed to the high BESS cost, which reduced profit margins under the current trading and electricity price structure and thereby restricted the solar PV scale. This conclusion can be validated by conducting sensitivity analysis by adopting a lower battery cost (see the detailed results in Figs. S2–S5 of **supplementary material**). When the battery installation price ($C_{\text{battery}} \times R_{\text{ec}}$) reduced from current 450 GBP·kWh⁻¹ to 350 GBP·kWh⁻¹, 250 GBP·kWh⁻¹, and 150 GBP·kWh⁻¹, a trend toward higher penetration of solar PVs was recommended with an upscaled integration of BESS. These configurations introduced an additional 1.27 GWh, 0.48 GWh, and 0.94 GWh of solar energy to the campus energy system, respectively, contributing to an increase in the annual net profit to 2.12 m GBP, 2.95 m GBP, and 3.32 m GBP. (ii) Relatively high economic gains were achieved through the net metering trading in Spring compared to other seasons. One of the necessary conditions for this outcome was the

Fig. 7. Day-ahead trading price (C_{DA}).

combination of large surplus energy and a relatively low DA trading pricing structure, which occurred during the 16th and 35th time segments. In other seasons, this necessary condition was rarely met (71st to 73rd time segments in Summer), therefore, leading to lower profits from net metering. (iii) The optimal initial SOC of different season was quantified based on complicated interrelated factors under DA trading. According to the optimisation results shown in Fig. 8, a qualitative analysis could be conducted to investigate the elements that influence the optimisation. As seen in Fig. 7, day-ahead trading prices were typically lower at the beginning and end of the day cycle in spring and summer than other seasons. The profit margins generated against the low-peak electricity price were not sufficient to compensate the depreciation cost of BESS. Consequently, as illustrated in Fig. 8A and B, batteries were primarily charged at low-peak electricity prices at day-end and following day-start aiming for a later energy trading at a high trading price. In comparison, higher trading prices were available at day-start and day-end sections in autumn and winter seasons, and sufficient profit margins were available for the batteries to generate income by trading the low-peak electricity. Therefore, the batteries were discharged to participate in day-ahead trading near day-end and during day-start. This profit margin-driven behaviour of the BESS can be considered as a factor that affects the optimal value of initial SOC. Additionally, as indicated in Figs. S2–S5 in the **supplementary material**, the decrease in the cost of the BESS also contribute to the determination of best initial SOC through increasing profit margin against the low-peak electricity price and altering the optimal number of batteries and solar PV. This situation where the optimal solution for economic improvement cannot be obtained through separated assessment of a single element, on the other hand, verifies the necessity of using artificial intelligence to conduct interdependent design and operation.

4.4. System performance with introduction of dynamic frequency trading (Scenario V)

Dynamic Frequency was another main trading mechanism employed in battery business activities. Referring to Fig. 9 [38,44], when grid frequency exceeds fr_{upper} , incomes can be generated through charging the batteries using the electricity from the grid at the designated ratio (DFH service). On the other hand, discharging batteries at the required power ratio when frequency drops below fr_{lower} can also yield economic gains (DFL service). Additionally, the introduction of the BESS can create economic benefits by maintaining in standby mode when grid frequency remains within the two thresholds. The prices for DF trading were shown in Fig. 10 [45]. It should be noted that auctions are required

before engaging in the DF service and unsuccessful auction could happen which was considered in this research and marked as red crosses in Fig. 10.

The optimisation results recommended an integration of 175 MWh/1 C-rate of BESS and 23.52 MW of solar PVs to achieve a maximum annual profit of 7.37 m GBP for the campus energy system. The scale of the BESS and capacity rate reached the upper limit provided for the optimisation (maximum number of batteries was 5000 and maximum capacity rate was 1). The reason for this result is: as demonstrated in Eq. (16), the income generated from the DF trading depends on the installed battery capacity and equipped power ratio of the inverter. This implies the fact that once the provided annual profit from the DF service per BESS unit exceeds its depreciation cost and the expenses for maintaining the consistency of the SOC, the scale of the BESS and equipped capacity rate would reach the defined maximum limit. This case fits the situation. The calculation results using Eq. (12) demonstrated that the operating power of the battery used in DF service accounts for <3 % of its rate power, therefore, the influence of SOC maintaining cost on the economic optimisation would be insignificant.

The operation strategy of the batteries was shown in Fig. 11A and B, and the economic flow of the system operation was provided in Fig. 11C. It can be learned that the overall operation of the batteries was motivated by the DF trading mechanism, and the profitability of the system were mainly oriented from the participation in DF service. In spring, a profit of 27,887 GBP was achieved from the DF trading, and due to the large amounts of surplus energy available from the campus system, additional gain of 7813 GBP was obtained from net metering trading. After deducting the operating expenses of the BESS and solar PVs and the electricity bill for load demand, a net daily profit of 4293 GBP was achieved. In summer, lack of surplus energy from the campus resulted in none of profit from the net metering trading, leading to a higher electricity bill. However, a relatively high trading price for DF was available to increase the economic benefit to 75,513 GBP, leading to a net profit gain of the 35,220 GBP per day. A low DF service fee in autumn case limited economic gains to 37,638 GBP, and as was the case in the summer, no additional income from the net metering trading brought owing to the absence of surplus energy. To fill in the gap of load demand and compensate the cost of storage and renewable device, a daily net deficit of 378 GBP occurred. Referring to Fig. 10, in the winter season, high DF trading prices similar to those in summer case generated an economic gain of 77,797 GBP. Sporadic excess energy was exported through net metering trading and contributed to generating 713 GBP of profits, leading to a seasonal high net profit of 44,882 GBP per day.

Based on the optimisation results, further discussions need to be

Fig. 8. System performance under DA trading (Scenario IV) (A) Power of the battery, (B) SOC of the battery, and (C) Economic flow.

Fig. 9. Frequency of dynamic frequency trading.

Fig. 10. Price of dynamic frequency trading (A) DFH price, (B) DFL price.

Fig. 11. System performance under DF trading (A) Power of the battery, (B) SOC of the battery, and (C) Economic flow.

conducted to clarify the optimisation mechanism with the introduction of DF service. (i) in spring and winter cases, parts of the released power from the battery were used for net metering trading or load compensation. This was not because surplus energy from the campus was available in these seasons but due to the provided structure of power frequency. To achieve a greater profit, more charging power for DFH than that discharged for DFL was induced according to the frequency of DF service in these seasons. As a result, extra stored energy in the battery can be released for net metering services and load compensation during the segments where the trading price for DF was the lowest (Segment 29 and 30 in Spring, and Segment 167 and 174 in Winter), and in the meantime, facilitating the maintenance of the initial and end SOC in an operation cycle. On the other hand, the charged power via DFH service can be deemed as a cost-free energy like solar power. The participation in the net metering service using this energy can occupy the capacity of substation and limit the scale of solar PVs integrated into the system. Therefore, a lower scale of 23.52 MW of solar PVs compared to the scenarios of involving sole net metering trading and additional day-ahead trading was suggested to obtain the best economic benefits. The maximum operating capacity of substation reached 17.97 MW at segment 29 where the BESS were in discharging mode for participating in net metering trading. (ii) Surplus energy from the campus was used solely for net metering trading and load compensation while none of them was utilised to charge the batteries. This was mainly since the charging behaviour using surplus energy conflicted with the participation in DFH service and reduce profitability. (iii) The economic gain of the system was primarily driven by the DF trading and the corresponding power fluctuations were relatively low ($<3\%$ of rated power). As the battery round-trip efficiency at different SOC conditions were considered identical in the current study, altering the current optimised initial SOC value for each season (as shown in Fig. 11B) downward to guarantee any SOC value within the range between SOC_{lower} and SOC_{upper} would not affect the overall optimisation outcome.

To validate the feasibility of the optimisation results, further evaluations of the system performance were conducted. Fig. 6B demonstrates the annual carbon emissions of the campus system which were estimated by net energy input/output to the grid (= CHP generation + solar PVs generation – load demand – battery charge (grid) + battery discharge), temporal generation data in 2022 [46], and the generation-based CO₂ emissions [47,48]. The carbon emissions of original system (Scenario I) reached 8051 ton per year. Scenario III stood out in carbon reduction decreasing by 61.4 % of the original system because of the largest scale of solar PV deployment. Same scale of solar PVs was employed in Scenario IV, however, the energy loss in the battery operation led to a less carbon reduction rate to 50.3 %. The carbon emissions of the campus system reduced by 33.1 % and 28.5 % in Scenario V and Scenario II, respectively, as the size of the solar system gradually decreased. The lifetime of the campus energy system is determined by the component with the shortest lifespan, which was the battery in this study. Referring to Fig. 6C, Scenarios I, II and III possessed the longest service lifetime of 20 years which was determined by calendar life of the solar panels. The campus energy system had the shortest lifetime of 3.6 years in Scenario IV, which was attributed to the active operation of the BESS for participating in the day-ahead trading with great consuming of its life cycles. In Scenario V, although active operation of the BESS was found in the engagement in the DF trading, the batteries could serve their calendar lifetime of 10 years owing to the minor operation-dependent degradation. Fig. 6D shows the payback cycle for solar PVs and BESS investments, which was calculated as total investment cost divided by economic improvements compared to the original system. Scenario IV possessed the shortest payback period of 4.1 years, which exceeded its lifetime. This indicated that the system would not be able to recover the investment cost within the effective service life of existing batteries, leading to an economic deficit to the stakeholders. This situation could be improved by reducing the investment cost of the battery. The sensitivity analysis results in the **supplementary material** (Fig. S5) showed

that the system lifetime would exceed the payback time when the battery investment cost decreased to 350, 250, and 150 GBP·kWh⁻¹. The highest net profit gains among others were obtained in Scenario V. However, considering the huge investment for the large scale of BESS, a payback cycle of 4.8 years was achieved. Longer service lifetimes can be achieved in Scenarios II and III, while a relatively long payback durations of 16.7 and 10.8 years were provided owing to the low economic profits generated.

5. Conclusions

In this study, a new intelligent framework using advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) was developed for the economic viable decarbonisation process of local energy systems. The combination of the artificial networks of energy flows and an upgraded evolutionary algorithm incorporating artificial domestication theory was successfully achieved to decouple complex interactions in the economic flows and deal with nonlinearities in optimisation. Simultaneous design and operation optimisation of solar photovoltaics (PVs) and battery energy storage systems (BESS) was implemented for a local energy system working in the University of Warwick to enhance economic performance in energy supply. Based on the optimisation results and system performance across different trading mechanisms, the following conclusions could be drawn:

- (i) The proposed intelligent approach effectively accounts for operation-dependent degradation of the batteries and the corresponding cost and provided sufficient flexibility to the determination of the operation strategy to further explore profitability margin. The complicated interactions of design parameters (total capacity of solar PVs and BESS, and power ratio of battery inverter) and operation parameters (initial SOCs, operation flags, charge/discharge power, and trading flags of the BESS) in economic flow were comprehensively addressed through the coupled modelling development and artificial network establishment. Furthermore, the complexity brought in by the introduction of design and operation dependant trading mechanisms were also embedded in the artificial network. The adopted Biogeography-Based Optimisation (BBO) approach integrated with artificial domestication process possessed an outstanding capability to solve the interdependent economic optimisation problems characterising high nonlinearities.
- (ii) Without any trading mechanism, the blind enlargement of the solar PVs' scalability was economically unfeasible and was restricted because of the export of surplus generation to the grid without any profit gain. On the other hand, the high cost of battery technology was the main obstacle to hinder its integration with the solar PVs. Sufficient margin between the low-peak and high-peak time-of-use (ToU) prices, and surplus energy from the local generation could facilitate the application of the BESS for peak-shaving. Therefore, the efforts should be taken to issue an exporting license with the Distributed System Operator (DSO) to increase the profit paths of local energy systems. Supported by the enhanced profitability, greater carbon reduction could be achieved by the deployment of more renewable energy.
- (iii) The introduction of the net metering (NM) trading could facilitate the scaling of solar PVs since the improved economic gains outweighed the depreciation cost. In this context, the more installation of the PVs, the more economic income could be obtained, and the greater carbon reduction could be achieved. However, the determination of the PV capacity was constrained by the export limit of the substation capacity to the grid, exceeding which would cause serious safety and reliability issues in energy supply. Considering a high cost of BESS, the tariff arbitrage from the peak shaving under the ToU pricing structure was not an economic viable option.

- (iv) The adoption of day-ahead trading (DA) could provide enough arbitrary margin for introducing the BESS to the system to improve the economic benefits. The operating principle of the BESS in maximising profitability was all the released power from the batteries were used to participate in the day-ahead trading, while no contribution was made to reduce the discrepancy of energy demand. In the seasons where higher trading prices were provided, the batteries operated over the calendar cycles to boost economic gains (e.g., spring, autumn, and winter cases); otherwise, the operation cycle life of the batteries was optimised to the value equal to that calculated by the calendar lifetime, to compensate the desperation cost through day-ahead trading (e.g., summer case). Under the current structure of ToU and trading prices, the expected picture of expanding the solar PVs through integrating more BESS to meet substation export limit proved unfeasible. One of reasons was reduction in the profit margins would occur because of the high BESS cost.
- (v) When the dynamic frequency (DF) was introduced, the optimal capacity of the BESS would reach the defined maximum limit once the provided annual profit from the DF service per BESS unit exceeds its depreciation cost and the expenses for maintaining SOC consistency. It was worth noting that, surplus campus energy was avoided to charge the batteries because the charging behaviour conflicted with the participation in DFH service and led to the reduction in profit gains. Additionally, the stored power in the batteries via DFH service could be utilised to participate in the NM service, and this could occupy the capacity of substation and reduce the scale of solar PVs.
- (vi) Further evaluation of the system performance demonstrated that more deployment of the solar PVs yielded higher carbon reductions. In Scenario III, the highest carbon reduction rate of 61.4 % was achieved. The integration of BESS could increase carbon emission owing to the energy loss in the battery operation (with DA trading) or decrease in the solar PV scale (with DF trading). However, the profitability of the system could be significantly improved. Under the DA trading mechanism, the payback cycle exceeded the system service time because of the severe loss in battery lifetime cycles. Although reducing battery installation costs will help improve this situation, an expected payback period shorter than the system's lifetime should be set as an input in the framework with the introduction of DA trading, thereby avoiding excessive economic losses due to premature battery replacement. The adoption of DF trading mechanism could achieve the highest economic gains and maintain a relatively long service life of the system and a reasonable payback cycle.

The proposed intelligent framework can generate a cost-effective roadmap for decarbonising local energy systems, allowing for easy adaption to specific carbon reduction targets by setting a penalty threshold (exceeding the emissions limit incurs a significant financial penalty). This framework enables in-depth analysis of key economic performance drivers by accessing the optimisation mechanism. Additionally, an efficient tool could be provided to make up for the lack of economic benefits from design and scheduling of system in traditional economic estimates. Moreover, various incentive policies can be integrated into the framework to assess their impact on profit margins, helping determine the most effective strategies for economic and environmental gains.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Dacheng Li: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Songshan Guo:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Formal analysis. **Jihong Wang:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Yongliang Li:** Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Chengong Sun: Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Geng Qiao:** Resources. **Chaomurilige:** Resources. **Yulong Ding:** Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) of the United Kingdom (Grant No EP/V041665/1). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101007976. Finally, the authors are grateful to Warwick university Estates for giving the access to data server.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.egyai.2025.100505](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyai.2025.100505).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] Rae C, Kerr S, Maroto-Valer MM. Upscaling smart local energy systems: a review of technical barriers. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2020;131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110020>.
- [2] SolarPowerEurope. Global market outlook for solar power 2024-2028; 2024.
- [3] Khezri R, Mahmoudi A, Aki H. Optimal planning of solar photovoltaic and battery storage systems for grid-connected residential sector: review, challenges and new perspectives. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111763>.
- [4] Schleifer AH, Murphy CA, Cole WJ, Denholm PL. The evolving energy and capacity values of utility-scale PV-plus-battery hybrid system architectures. *Adv Appl Energy* 2021;2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adapen.2021.100015>.
- [5] Fosso Tajouo G, Tiam Kapen P, Djanna Koffi FL. Techno-economic investigation of an environmentally friendly small-scale solar tracker-based PV/wind/battery hybrid system for off-grid rural electrification in the mount bamboutos, Cameroon. *Energy Strat Rev* 2023;48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2023.101107>.
- [6] Memon SA, Upadhyay DS, Patel RN. Optimization of solar and battery-based hybrid renewable energy system augmented with bioenergy and hydro energy-based dispatchable source. *iScience* 2023;26(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.105821>.
- [7] O'Shaughnessy E, Cutler D, Ardani K, Margolis R. Solar plus: optimization of distributed solar PV through battery storage and dispatchable load in residential buildings. *Appl Energy* 2018;213:11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.12.118>.
- [8] Gür TM. Review of electrical energy storage technologies, materials and systems: challenges and prospects for large-scale grid storage. *Energy Environ Sci* 2018;11(10):2696–767. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8ee01419a>.
- [9] Elalfy DA, Gouda E, Kotb MF, Bureš V, Sedhom BE. Comprehensive review of energy storage systems technologies, objectives, challenges, and future trends. *Energy Strat Rev* 2024;54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101482>.
- [10] Ping D, Li C, Yu X, Liu Z, Tu R, Zhou Y. City-scale information modelling for urban energy resilience with optimal battery energy storages in Hong Kong. *Appl Energy* 2025;378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.124813>.
- [11] Mendes Ferreira Gomes A, Xavier de Andrade Pinto G, Rütther R. Techno-economic assessment of small-size residential solar PV + battery systems under different tariff structures in Brazil. *Sol Energy* 2024;267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2023.112238>.
- [12] Pena-Bello A, Barbour E, Gonzalez MC, Patel MK, Parra D. Optimized PV-coupled battery systems for combining applications: impact of battery technology and geography. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2019;112:978–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.06.003>.
- [13] Irshad AS, Ludin GA, Masrur H, et al. Optimization of grid-photovoltaic and battery hybrid system with most technically efficient PV technology after the performance analysis. *Renew Energy* 2023;207:714–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.03.062>.
- [14] McLaren J, Laws N, Anderson K, DiOrio N, Miller H. Solar-plus-storage economics: what works where, and why? *Electr J* 2019;32(1):28–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ej.2019.01.006>.

- [15] Pan X, Khezri R, Mahmoudi A, Muyeen SM. Optimal planning of solar PV and battery storage with energy management systems for time-of-use and flat electricity tariffs. *IET Renew Power Gener* 2022;16(6):1206–19. <https://doi.org/10.1049/rpg2.12433>.
- [16] Huang P, Sun Y, Lovati M, Zhang X. Solar-photovoltaic-power-sharing-based design optimization of distributed energy storage systems for performance improvements. *Energy* 2021;222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.119931>.
- [17] Duan F, Eslami M, Khajehzadeh M, Basem A, Jasim DJ, Palani S. Optimization of a photovoltaic/wind/battery energy-based microgrid in distribution network using machine learning and fuzzy multi-objective improved Kepler optimizer algorithms. *Sci Rep* 2024;14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-64234-x>.
- [18] Tian Y, Chang J, Wang Y, Wang X, Meng X, Guo A. The capacity planning method for a hydro-wind-PV-battery complementary system considering the characteristics of multi-energy integration into power grid. *J Clean Prod* 2024;446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141292>.
- [19] Jayawardana A, Agalgaonkar AP, Robinson DA, Fiorentini M. Optimisation framework for the operation of battery storage within solar-rich microgrids. *IET Smart Grid* 2019;2(4):504–13. <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-stg.2019.0084>.
- [20] Sani Hassan A, Cipcigan L, Jenkins N. Optimal battery storage operation for PV systems with tariff incentives. *Appl Energy* 2017;203:422–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.06.043>.
- [21] Kappner K, Letmathe P, Weidinger P. Optimisation of photovoltaic and battery systems from the prosumer-oriented total cost of ownership perspective. *Energy Sustain Soc* 2019;9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-019-0231-2>.
- [22] Zhou Y. Renewable-storage sizing approaches for centralized and distributed renewable energy—a state-of-the-art review. *J Energy Storage* 2024;100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.113688>.
- [23] Samantaray S, Kayal P. Capacity assessment and scheduling of battery storage systems for performance and reliability improvement of solar energy enhanced distribution systems. *J Energy Storage* 2023;66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.107479>.
- [24] Baniasadi A, Habibi D, Al-Saedi W, Masoum MAS, Das CK, Mousavi N. Optimal sizing design and operation of electrical and thermal energy storage systems in smart buildings. *J Energy Storage* 2020;28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2019.101186>.
- [25] Mariaud A, Acha S, Ekins-Daukes N, Shah N, Markides CN. Integrated optimisation of photovoltaic and battery storage systems for UK commercial buildings. *Appl Energy* 2017;199:466–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.04.067>.
- [26] The Royal Society. A net zero climate-resilient future – science, technology and the solutions for change. Published online 2021.
- [27] Fu R., Remo T., Margolis R. 2018 U.S. utility-scale photovoltaics-plus-energy storage system costs benchmark; 2018. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy19osti/71714.pdf>.
- [28] Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. Solar photovoltaic (PV) cost data; 2024. Accessed January 6, 2025. <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/solar-pv-cost-data>.
- [29] IRENA. Renewable power generation costs in 2023. *International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi*; 2024.
- [30] Hao M, Li J, Park S, Moura S, Dames C. Efficient thermal management of Li-ion batteries with a passive interfacial thermal regulator based on a shape memory alloy. *Nat Energy* 2018;3(10):899–906. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-018-0243-8>.
- [31] Li J, Gee AM, Zhang M, Yuan W. Analysis of battery lifetime extension in a SMES-battery hybrid energy storage system using a novel battery lifetime model. *Energy* 2015;86:175–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.03.132>.
- [32] Ranaweera I, Midtgård OM, Korpås M. Distributed control scheme for residential battery energy storage units coupled with PV systems. *Renew Energy* 2017;113:1099–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2017.06.084>.
- [33] Jathar LD, Ganesan S, Awasarmol U, et al. Comprehensive review of environmental factors influencing the performance of photovoltaic panels: concern over emissions at various phases throughout the lifecycle. *Environ Pollut* 2023;326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121474>.
- [34] Libra M, Mrázek D, Tyukhov I, et al. Reduced real lifetime of PV panels – economic consequences. *Sol Energy* 2023;259:229–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2023.04.063>.
- [35] Dufo-López R, Bernal-Agustín JL. Techno-economic analysis of grid-connected battery storage. *Energy Convers Manag* 2015;91:394–404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2014.12.038>.
- [36] Western power distribution (West Midlands) plc use of system charging statement notice of charges effective from 1st April 2023.
- [37] DESNZ. Incremental reforms to wholesale electricity markets review of wholesale electricity markets; 2023.
- [38] National Grid Electricity System Operator. Dynamic containment testing guidelines; 2020.
- [39] Simon D. Biogeography-based optimization. *IEEE Trans Evolut Comput* 2008;12(6):702–13. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2008.919004>.
- [40] Zeller U, Göttert T. The relations between evolution and domestication reconsidered - implications for systematics, ecology, and nature conservation. *Glob Ecol Conserv* 2019;20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00756>.
- [41] Time and Date A.S.. Weather in Warwickshire. England: United Kingdom; 2022. <https://www.timeanddate.com/weather/@2634723>. [Accessed January 6, 2025].
- [42] Idaho National Laboratory. Battery technology life verification test manual revision 1. 2012. <http://www.inl.gov>.
- [43] Epexspot. Trading product. Accessed January 6, 2025. <https://www.epexspot.com/en>.
- [44] Elexon Support. Rolling system frequency. Accessed January 6, 2025. <https://bmr.s.elexon.co.uk/rolling-system-frequency>.
- [45] National Energy System Operator (NESO). Enduring Auction Capability (EAC) auction results. Accessed January 6, 2025. <https://www.neso.energy/data-portal/eac-auction-results>.
- [46] Data courtesy of Elexon portal and Sheffield University. G.B. national grid status. 2024. Accessed January 6, 2025. <https://www.gridwatch.templar.co.uk/download.php>.
- [47] Parliamentary office of Science and Technology. *Carbon footprint of electricity generation*; 2011.
- [48] Wilson IAG, Staffell I. Rapid fuel switching from coal to natural gas through effective carbon pricing. *Nat Energy* 2018;3(5):365–72. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-018-0109-0>.